

April 30, 2020

Forms of Inoculant, Shelf-Life Studies and Formulations of Orchid Mycorrhizal Fungi (OMF) Inoculants

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effectiveness of the inoculants in different forms and their shelf-life six months and one year after storage at room temperature using orchid plants such as Dendrobium, Catleya and Vanda as the host plants. The parameters used include height, biomass, leaf area and number of psuedo-bulbs. Formulations of the different inoculants were likewise assessed for their techno-feasibility and viability. Plants inoculated with different forms of inoculants either spawn 1 (rice bran and sawdust) and spawn 2 (rice bran and fern chips) or fruiting bodies stored for 6 months or one year were significantly taller than their uninoculated counterparts. Inoculated plants were generally more vigorous, healthier and produced thicker roots than the uninoculated control. Differences among inoculated plants were insignificant indicating that spawn 1 and spawn 2 were as effective as the fruiting bodies and spores of OMF. Chopped fruiting bodies, mixture of sawdust and spores and spawn were techno-feasible into a tablet form while pulverized fruiting bodies and spores mixed with fine filler could not be formed into tablet. The inoculants in different formulations were still viable 7 months after storage at room temperature.

Keywords: formulation, inoculant, shelf-life, orchid mycorrhizal fungi

Abbreviation: OMF- orchid mycorrhizal fungi

INTRODUCTION

If the seeds are spread on moist substratum the embryos undifferentiated but do not develop further unless it is provided with an exogenous supply of nutrients or is infected by a compatible mycorrhizal fungus right after their germination.

Great efforts in research have been made on the role of mycorrhizal fungi in seed germination and its early growth in 18th century (Arditti, 1992). However, the function of mycorrhizal association in adult green orchids has received attention only recently (Brown et al, 1997). Research on OMF in the country just started in 1995 in BIOTECH at Vesicular-arbuscular Mycorrhiza (VAM) Laboratory. Since then, numerous studies related to OMF have been conducted by the group including its effect on in-vitro cultured *Dendrobium* (Brown et al. 1997) and *Vanda* (Brown et al. 1999). Their long-term effect on orchid plants as growth enhancer (Brown et al. 2001) and as biocontrol agent of root pathogen infection has already been documented (BIOTECH Terminal Report 2001).

A number of orchid fungi have been isolated, screened for their effectiveness, characterized (Brown et al. 1997), and classified based on their morphological growth, histological characteristics (Yago et al. 2004) and on

April 30, 2020

their ability to synthesize mycorrhiza in axenic conditions (Brown et al. 2004). Non-pathogenic isolates have been separated from pathogenic ones by PCR-Based method (Yago et al. 2004).

Since orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) are being touted as possible healthier and inexpensive alternatives to other fertilizers, pesticides, and even fungicides, it is important to study the forms of inoculant and shelf-life of OMF inoculants for commercial application. The substrates for propagation of these OMF should also be tested for their compatibility with the intended host plant.

Initially, finely chopped-fruiting bodies and pure culture in the form of mycelia and sclerotial bodies were used as an inoculants (Brown et al, 2004.). There were however some drawbacks in commercial application to these inoculants. These include the unavailability of fruiting bodies or spores in large quantity throughout the year since fruiting formation in nature is seasonal and the long period of its production in artificial conditions. Mycelia and sclerotial bodies although can be easily mass-produced were difficult to apply and they can be easily affected by environmental stress like drought, moisture or water once they germinated. Sclerotial bodies and spores can be easily washed away from compots during watering especially when charcoal are used as potting medium in community pots.

Recently the technique for spawn production using different substrate was found to be feasible (Brown et al., 2005). However their effectiveness must have to be tested and compared to finely chopped fruiting bodies. Their shelf-life should be determined, identified and compared to other forms of inoculants prior to large-scale application. Various formulations of the different forms of inoculant have to be evaluated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In-vivo Evaluation and Shelf-life Studies of the Different Forms of Inoculants

Pot experiments were conducted to determine the effectiveness of different forms of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies, spawn and spores). Simultaneously, the shelf life of these potential inoculants was evaluated six months and a year after storing them at room temperature. The substrates that was used in producing spawn were the combination of 1:1 ratio of rice bran and fern chips (spawn 1) and rice bran and sawdust (spawn 2). Finely chopped fruiting bodies and uninoculated control were included in the treatments to serve as a check and standard. The inoculation of the fruiting bodies and mycorrhizal spawn was done during the repotting activity. The experiment was laid-out in a modified completely randomized design. The effectiveness of mycorrhizal spawn was evaluated by measuring the growth increment and survival rates of inoculated seedlings. Plant height, biomass, leaf area and number of pseudo-bulbs were evaluated. The set up was maintained under glass house conditions.

Based on the previous studies, the growth of *Cattleya* and *Vanda* fertilized with half the manufacturer's recommended rate was comparable to the growth of plants fertilized with full dose manufacturer's recommended rate. This was the basis for the blanket application of 30-10-10 at half recommended rate (1g/L solution) in this study. The fertilizer solution was sprayed on the leaves and roots of the plants although a portion of the spray solution lodged on the potting medium. Application was carried out twice a week. Six months after planting another inorganic compound fertilizer (19-19-19) was applied using the same rate as the first formulation. Plant height and number of pseudo-bulbs produced per plant were gathered while flowering period was not determined yet. *Cattleya* and *Vanda spp.* are naturally slow growing plants thus it would take some time before results for flowering period will be available.

Techno-Eco Feasibility of Formulated Inoculants and Shelf-Life Studies of OMF

This study was conducted to investigate the viability of different tablets that was formulated; T1- rice bran + spores, T2- chopped fruiting bodies, T3- sawdust + spawn and T4- sawdust + spawn. One hundred grams of dried powdered formulation was added with 50 micro liters of diluted magnesium stearate. After mixing, two hundred grams of each of the formulated inoculant was properly mixed. The combined powdered forms of inoculant were prepared using number 18 at 100 mm sieve. Mixed formulation was tabletized using tableting machine developed at BIOTECH. The weight of the tablet was exactly 15 grams. These were packed in plastic tumbler and stored at room temperature while not in used and for succeeding experiments.

Viability test was conducted using slide germination test of the tablet forms of spores and mycelia from spawn. A method developed by Tuite (1984) was followed in counting spores using haemocytometer. Total spores of 4.2×10^3 were used in the test. Known number of spores was germinated using slide germination test and laid-out in sterilized plates with moist filter paper. Plates were incubated and refrigerated for 24 hours before counting germinated spores. Single strand of OMF mycelia were measured at 6 mm which was used to test the viability of spawn. Six single mycelia were picked and laid-out at the center of the slides. This was replicated three times. Sterilized fifty micro liters of distilled water was dropped at the center of the slides. This was incubated for 24 hours at room temperature. Number of germinated and ungerminated spores was recorded. Lateral germination of mycelia was also counted. The number of germinated and ungerminated spores and mycelia were divided by known number of tested spores and mycelia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In-vivo Evaluation and Shelf-life Studies of the Different Forms of Inoculants

Effectiveness of mycorrhizal fungi spawn as inoculant for Dendrobium six months after storage at room temperature

The results of our previous study on OMF spawn as inoculant paved the way for suitability evaluation of locally materials as substrates for the growth of mycelia. Based on the results of our screening, two combinations, namely; rice bran + fern chips and rice bran + sawdust were found highly suitable substrates. For spawn production, however, the shelf-life of these possible inoculants have not yet been evaluated. Thus, two types of OMF spawn (Spawn 1 and Spawn 2) corresponding to these two combinations of substrates were evaluated and compared with fruiting bodies using *Dendrobium* as test plant. The results showed that the plants inoculated with spawn 1 and 2 were generally bigger than the control and comparatively the uninoculated plants (Fig. 1). Plants inoculated with Spawn 2 were significantly taller than those inoculated with either Spawn 1 or fruiting bodies (Fig. 2). The inoculated plants had statistically the same total leaf area (Fig. 3). The number of pseudo-bulbs produced per plant as may be influenced by the form of OMF inoculant is very important because this determines flower productivity. At this stage of the study, the test plants still have to bear flowers.

April 30, 2020

Spawn 1- OMF propagated in rice bran + fern chips

Spawn 2- OMF propagated in rice bran + saw dust

Fig. 1. Growth performance of *Dendrobium* as affected by different sources of mycorrhizal inoculants (fruiting bodies and spawn) six months after storage at room temperature.

April 30, 2020

Fig. 2. Comparative effects of different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies and spawn) on plant height of *Dendrobium* plants (12 month old).

Spawn 1 - OMF propagated in rice bran + fern chips
 Spawn 2 - OMF propagated in rice bran + saw dust

Fig. 3. Leaf area of *Dendrobium* plants as affected by different sources of orchid mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies and spawn)

Effectiveness of mycorrhizal fungi spawn as inoculant for Vanda one year after storage at room temperature

In an attempt to determine the efficacy of OMF inoculants across orchid species, we evaluated the response of *Vanda* to OMF using fruiting bodies and spawn as the inoculants. The results of the study showed that *Vanda*

April 30, 2020

responded positively to these two types of OMF inoculants (Fig. 4) a year after storage at room temperature. The inoculated plants were generally bigger, and produced longer leaves and thicker roots than the uninoculated ones. Plants inoculated with either fruiting bodies or spawn had the same height and was significantly taller than the uninoculated control (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Comparative effects of different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies and spawn) on plant height of Vanda plants (12 month old).

Fig. 4. Growth response of Vanda plants to different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies and spawn).

Effectiveness of orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) inoculants for Cattleya one year after storage

On the basis of the results of our previous studies, two OMF inoculants in the form of finely-chopped fruiting bodies and spores were found effective for *Cattleya*. The effectiveness of the newly-developed form of inoculant, the spawn was compared from the previously used inoculants. The results of this study showed that the inoculated plants (regardless of the form of inoculant used) were generally more robust than the control (Fig. 6). Inoculated plants were healthier, had glossy foliage and thicker roots than the control. Differences among inoculated plants in terms of height (Fig. 7) and number of pseudo-bulbs per plant (Fig. 8) were not significant indicating that the OMF spawn was as effective as the fruiting bodies and spores of OMF.

Fig. 6. Growth response of *Cattleya* plants to different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies, spawn and spores).

April 30, 2020

Fig. 7. Comparative effects of different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies, spawn and spores) on plant height of *Cattleya* plants (12 month old).

Fig. 8. Comparative effects of different sources of mycorrhizal fungi inoculants (fruiting bodies, spawn and spores) on pseudo-bulb production per plant (12 month old).

Techno-Eco Feasibility of Formulated Inoculants

All powdered forms of formulations were technically feasible (Table 1). Out of the four formulation, chopped fruiting bodies + spores, sawdust + spores and sawdust + spawn were techno-feasible into a tablet forms (Fig. 9). The study found out that fine formulation was not feasible because it could not form a tablet. It was recommended therefore that sieving technique-using number 18 at 100 mm sieve be used for better formulation.

Table 1. Techno-feasibility of four formulated OMF inoculants.

SUBSTRATE	FORMS OF INOCULANT*	
	Powder	Tablet
Rice bran + spores,	+	-
Chopped fruiting bodies	+	+
Sawdust + spores	+	+
Sawdust + spawn.	+	+

* - = not feasible
 + = feasible

April 30, 2020

Fig. 9. Formulated tablets. A. Chopped fruiting bodies, B. Sawdust + spores, C. sawdust + spawn.

After seven months of storage, the data indicated that mixture of rice bran and spores, sawdust and spores, and sawdust and spawn have the highest germination percentage (Fig. 10). These three-powdered formulations can be used because it has a comparable effect. However, germination ability of chopped fruiting bodies decreased significantly by almost 18% because it recorded a germination ability of 82.44% compared to the above stated combined formulations.

April 30, 2020

Fig. 10. Percent viability of different sources of orchid mycorrhizal fungi (spores, fruiting bodies, spawn) in different forms 6 months after storage at room temperature.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study was conducted at the National Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology (BIOTECH), in Los Baños, Laguna from June 2005 to March 2006. This was a continuation and a part of the project that was started in 2003.

In-vivo experiments were conducted in the evaluation of the shelf-life and effectiveness of different forms of inoculant using *Dendrobium* as host plant for the six months of storage while the *Vanda* and *Cattleya* as the host plants for the shelf-life a year after storage.

Plants inoculated with spawn or fruiting bodies were significantly taller than the uninoculated control and that there appeared to be a difference in effectiveness between Spawn 1 and Spawn 2. Plants inoculated with Spawn 2 (using fern chips as substrate) were significantly taller than those inoculated with either Spawn 1 (using rice bran and saw dust) or fruiting bodies. *Vanda* and *Cattleya* responded positively to these two types of OMF spawn inoculant) a year after storage at room temperature. Plants inoculated with either fruiting bodies or spawn had the same average height and were significantly taller than their uninoculated counterparts. Inoculated plants had glossy foliage and thicker roots than the control. Differences among inoculated plants in terms of height (and number of pseudo-bulbs per plant were not significant indicating that the OMF spawns were as effective as the fruiting bodies and spores of OMF.

Studies were also conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of inoculants in different forms/formulations, and simultaneously to determine the shelf life of the different forms of inoculant six months and a year after storage at room temperature. The first experiment tried to investigate the viability of different tablets that was formulated; T1- rice bran + spores, T2- chopped fruiting bodies, T3- sawdust + spawn and T4- sawdust + spawn. Viability test was conducted using slide germination test of the tablet forms of spores and mycelia from spawn.

April 30, 2020

Different mixtures of powdered inoculants were allowed to pass through a tableting machine. All powdered forms of formulations were technically feasible. On the other hand, out of the four formulation, combination of chopped fruiting bodies and spores, sawdust and spores, and sawdust and spawn were techno-feasible into a tablet forms. Fine formulation like pure spores could not be made into. After seven months of storage, the data indicated that combination of rice bran and spores, sawdust and spores, and sawdust and spawn have the highest germination percentage.

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April 30, 2020

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